

New Realism as a Frame of Reference

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1.

There is a slogan printed on certain fashionable notebooks that says «Facts are the enemy of truth»: a quotation by Cervantes, used as a result of a very efficacious brand management. These are white notebooks of various formats, fitting any pocket, selling catchy phrases: in short, there is nothing new about them.

Now, I do not know whether 2011 will be remembered for the death of Postmodernism followed by the birth of New Realism, which has certainly been (for better or worse) the most debated subject of the past few years, and not a mere marketing operation as some had us believe.¹ The debate opened by Maurizio Ferraris went beyond all expectations: after all, the success of a media event can well be the outcome of

¹ You can see the debate here: inspired by the article <http://nuovorealismo.wordpress.com/rassegna/2011-2/>, Maurizio Ferraris, “Manifesto del Nuovo Realismo”, *La Repubblica*, (2011). The following year a book was published: Maurizio Ferraris, *Manifesto del nuovo realismo*, (Laterza, 2012). See also: Mario De Caro, Maurizio Ferraris (ed.), *Bentornata realtà* (Einaudi, 2012). For a punctual reconstruction of the media debate see: Raffaella Scarpa, *Il caso nuovo realismo. La lingua del dibattito filosofico contemporaneo* (Mimesis, 2013).

mere chance – otherwise we would have a secure formula for success in our hands. The book *Il pensiero debole* also had an unpredicted success. These two events were destined to intertwine.

New realism is strongly critical of weak thought, which is partly a form of self-criticism, as Ferraris has been protagonist in both movements. At the centre of the discussion we find the theme of truth, or rather, the presumed relativism of every truth. Now, it would be daring to call this a new topic. The beginning of philosophy itself coincides with the affirmation of something absolutely *stable*, capable of escaping the annihilating power of the becoming of things. This, at any rate, is what we are told about the history of philosophy.

The concept of *epistémè* that emerged in ancient Greece was characterised by absolute stability: its atemporality, in contrast to the temporality of the world, was interpreted as an attempt by the western metaphysical tradition to protect truth from the process of becoming.

The unconditional affirmation of truth reflects the redeeming power of the divine and the perfection of art itself, with a significant consequence: the truth of philosophy is not affirmed by faith or by some kind of vocation, but is assumed according to the sense of necessity expressed by the *logos*.

One may say that a history lasting more than two millennia must have some kind of foundation; and yet in this case, ironically, it does not work this way. The end is tragic: it was the necessity of the *logos* itself that guided us to the epilogue that brought to the

breaking and dissolution of truth – an exemplary case of euthanasia indeed.

2.

Absolute truth was meant to give mankind shelter from the ever-transforming and ever-destroying process of becoming; the same redeeming power today is ascribed to technology. Man wants to live and therefore searches for an escape from his mortality, in order to transcend his being-time. To grasp the truth implies the *stable* affirmation of the self, precisely that which *stays* still, that is not in becoming or remains “above” becoming: *epi-steme*. Truth cannot be in time, since if that were the case it would be subject to becoming-other; but truth cannot become-other than itself, otherwise it would not be what it is. Truth must therefore be identical to itself. Hence the strength of identity theory that “presumes”, or rather, finds in its own premises the need of truth.² On the contrary, weak thought inherits from Nietzsche the dissolution of truth (metaphysics), presenting itself as a practice rather than a new theory. Otherwise, the critique to the identity theory would be transformed into a new identity theory: the affirmation of the identity of difference. Is negating every absolute truth a truth in itself? If not, why should we take this affirmation into consideration? In

² See Emanuele Severino, *Nuovo realismo, vecchio dibattito. Tutto già conosciuto da millenni*, *Corriere della Sera*, (2011).

this case the only truth would be that there are no absolute truths.

3.

Identify theory is taken to entail a certain form of violence: in fact, we read that the affirmation of truth, of our identity, can only lead us to clash against the other. If we possess the truth and someone else does not think the same way as we do, he/she cannot but be mistaken. Therefore mediation is not possible. On the contrary, by negating the existence of absolute truths, we should learn to understand and to welcome the other, since we all participate in the game of truth that nobody definitively possesses. And yet, this would still imply the assumption of truth as a paradigm.

Weak thought surely appears more democratic, but the price to pay is still high if, in order to be more democratic, we have to do away with truth. It is a heavy loss, one that brings all of our assertions onto the same level: each of our values, each of our conquests of rights and civilisation could easily turn into its very opposite. If there is no right and wrong, beauty and ugliness, good and evil, true and false, then on what basis do we construct our civilisation? If everything is relative, then we cannot adopt the idea that universal rights exists, despise the evil of wars or reject death penalty. Even by adopting *one* thesis, without additional clarifications, in any case we would have lost something crucial. The gain of this “relativity” represents a meagre (albeit democratic) consolation, not

devoid of consequences on the ethical and aesthetic levels, as well as on the epistemological and metaphysical levels. Our actions, in fact, can never be better or worse than another, not even in the most extreme cases.

Reality, at this point, cannot but appear subjective, or rather subject to our will of power. The “strongest” writes the truth of history. Since truth *per se* does not exist, the strongest imposes his/her own truth to the weaker.³ Popper explained that democracy does not consist simply of a decision taken by a majority, but it includes the possibility that today’s minority can become tomorrow’s majority. In this way we can avoid the paradox by which a majority can suspend democracy itself. This implies a certain suspicion towards truth: democracy embodies the *doubt* that the majority represents the truth and for this reason it should always be self-correcting. It has been said that truth is precisely this: the perhaps infinite possibility of self-correction *towards* truth itself. In fact, if error exists, then its opposite must necessarily exist too. But does this imply being in truth or a possibility to arrive to truth?

4.

As a theory, new realism sets itself against assertions such as “everything is interpretation”, considered as emblematic of postmodernism. If *facts* no

longer exist, but there are only *interpretations*, then by the same principle we could negate everything, even concentration camps, the existence of which would be nothing but the product of our own interpretation of history.⁴

The anomaly is that nobody, or almost nobody, seems to bring forward this “relativistic” stance as their own. Yet, anyone who studied philosophy during the past twenty years will remember the subjectivist models typical of postmodern culture that today appear to be supported by no one. At the end of the 1980s, to call oneself a “realist” was equivalent to admitting to having a poor grasp of philosophy: a realist was seen as a simpleton who still believed that truths exist, that there is an external world and that things appear as they are, showing a lack of understanding of both philosophy after Nietzsche and contemporary philosophy in general.

Basically, realism stood for commonsense and not for philosophy. During those years, when a master such as Paolo Bozzi professed his realist “faith”, he clearly placed himself among a minority in respect to the prevailing fashions, both in philosophy and in psychology, for which the world was a subjective construction and the result of an interpretation. One might object that what was being denied was not the fact or the existence of an external world, but rather a uni-

³ The above thesis is developed by E. Severino in: Emanuele Severino, *La guerra*, (Rizzoli 1992).

⁴ See Ferraris, *Manifesto del Nuovo Realismo*, (2011); See Maurizio Ferraris, *Perseverare è diabolico*, *Alfa-beta2*, (2011).

vocal interpretation of that fact and that world.⁵

This position is shared by a substantial majority of the semioticians, in opposition to those concerned with the philosophy of perception, for whom not everything is “language”. The word “dog” does not bite: the world remains a ground of confrontation where our interpretations collapse. This world is a first shared frame of reference allowing for the coordination of our language and actions. We understand one another precisely because not everything is interpretation, otherwise the others and the world would remain something mysterious, even beyond philosophy. One could object that not everyone who engages with philosophy of perception subscribes to this position. To put it simply: we should be able to share a world, a reality that does not depend on us. If the world were solely “my world”, the other would remain something inscrutable for me.

Without a shared system of reference we would not be able to understand one another and we would be in the same situation as that famously described by Wittgenstein: “If a lion could talk we could not understand him”. A shared reality is the condition for different forms of life to be able to interact: no life system is closed and impermeable to its environment. And yet constructivism and cognitivism remain the paradigms of psychology. -Isms and fashions? Of course. But

⁵ See Pier Aldo Rovatti, *Inattualità del Pensiero Debole* (Forum, 2011).

they also include very different theoretical positions: there are those who believe that perception is direct, and those who on the contrary consider it to be dependent on superior activities such as thought, conceptual schemes and language. This theoretical difference grounds the point of view of those that think of the external world as “a matter of fact” and those that see it as a result of the construction of our conscience, our conceptual schemes, and more generally, of language.⁶

If we consider the relationship between the concept and the perceived as constitutive of perception, the world becomes a subjective representation. This is the presupposition that leads to doubting our perceptions. The appearance of the thing becomes the *result* of a concept. We perceive a cube only insofar as we *know* what a cube is: if we did not know the *definition* of it, we could not classify that object as *a* cube. The thing is what it is because it possesses a specific unity and identity based on the concept that identifies it. A geometrical entity lends itself to this kind of argument. Nevertheless, how many times in our life have we prepared a coffee without knowing how many sides a coffee-maker has?

⁶ See Diego Marconi, *Il postmoderno ucciso dalle sue caricature*, *la Repubblica* (2011).

5.

Back to our “debate” between new realism and postmodernity, one can notice a singular event: both of these philosophical traditions have been blaming each other for paving the way to totalitarianism. In the name of absolute truth one can declare wars, while in the name of negation one can negate concentration camps, understood as nothing but another way of interpreting history. This runs the risk of confusing the reader.

It can be argued that commonsense is more attuned to the relativist side, since philosophy continues to appear as the battlefield of endless controversies described by Kant. Are those who consider the postmodern condition insurmountable right? Should we bid truth farewell in order to embrace a progressive retreat into the infinite hermeneutics of the fact?

Art, the mirror of our time, has become completely subjective: in fact, it is believed that anything can become art. And yet, we can call ourselves postmodern, but we cannot expect to escape the art market. Contemporary art – subjective as it may be – possesses an objective value that is not intrinsic: it is worth as much as it is paid for. Art does not unveil the truth, but expresses its being as becoming: the passage from the thing to the work of art is without foundation, therefore anything can become art, even an artist’s shit. If everything is relative and if it is only a matter of taste, then how can the skills of a chef determine the prestige of a restaurant? The same thing is true for a

graphic designer or an architect: on what basis and what parameters do we appreciate their work? How do we evaluate something in a society where everything appears fluid? If everything were subjective, artists would not need any technique, nor any specialised language.

There seems to be some sense both in the affirmation of truth and in its negation. But here we are not trying to make opposites meet, nor are we attempting to find a new synthesis; we rather wish to re-think the sense of relativity itself. Relativity, as a matter of fact, does not necessarily bring us to the conclusion that everything is relative, and therefore that there is no such thing as absolute truth. “Truth” can be seen as an expression of the absolute or of totality, but here we are speaking of truth as always referring to a specific problem and limited to a specific frame of reference. This does not imply a constructivist approach, since the affirmation of a relatively stable part of the process is part of an autopoietic frame of reference *proper* of a given form of life, in a given environment. In this sense, there is no contradiction between “truth” and “process” .

Every form of life determines a system of relations, a structure in which to act, communicate, think. The emergent structures are something similar to “Kanizsa’s triangle”: a form emerges – which, according to the analysis of the distal stimulation (the physical stimulation) should not exist – the presence of which, from a phenomenological point of view, is undeniable, repeatable and shareable among subjects. In other words, it

is objective. Certain elements determine the emergence of a *complex* structure, one that cannot be reduced to its own underlying parts. The structure of truth is no exception. For example, we could say that there is no such thing as justice in an absolute sense, but given a specific situation and a specific context – representing the implicit frame of reference of our actions – we can still decide whether a decision is more or less just, and we can do this in a *non-*arbitrary way. The non-arbitrariness is offered by the “context”: the setting in which we act. This is true for every aspect: metaphysical, ontological, epistemological, ethical-normative and aesthetic.

6.

We continually evaluate works of art through the prism of a community or a narrative (art history, the artistic language), which determine paradigms and structures: these parameters mark the system of reference by which we judge an artwork. There is a margin of uncertainty, but still some artworks are good while others aren't. What are the *criteria* by which we evaluate them? We implicitly assume a frame of reference in order to express an opinion on an artwork: the art does not change, what changes is the frame of reference in which it is placed.

This becomes manifest in game-playing. In football, as in any other sport, given the rules we can judge the skills of a player, express an opinion on the game as a whole or

on a single action; at the end of the game we can elaborate a report for every single player or for the entire team, etc. On what basis could we do this, if there were no rules to structure the game and give value to a result rather than another? Let us try with another area of interest, like culinary art: in this case, too, given a shared and sufficiently stable value system, such as our body, we can recognise when a dish has been well prepared, independently from our personal *taste*. High cuisine can fail to meet our taste, but we would not judge it as unsuccessful for this reason: this fact is transcultural and intersubjective, so much so that we can learn, study and appreciate food, stories and traditions belonging to different populations.

We judge on the basis of frames of reference that we can assume, adopt or reject. Culinary art possesses its own rules, it is a craft that can be learned. The process of learning implies the adoption of certain *rules* that allow for something to be realised in a certain manner and not in another; it prescribes how to use colours in painting, or that pasta should be cooked in a certain manner, in order to obtain a specific result. In art as well as in sport, *training* takes us into the field of play which makes things, actions and works differently valuable and open to conjecture. Artworks, moreover, are successful when they harbour the rules of their own interpretation.

By reasoning within a specific context, defined by a specific purpose, the truth or falsity of certain assertions can be determined. Every assertion can be relativised, but such *relativity* is the premise both of the

affirmation of truth and of its negation in a wider context. In this sense, the relativity given by an implicit frame of reference in our discourse is the premise of the affirmation of truth and *not* its negation.

This concept can be clarified starting from the first implicit frame of reference constituted by our body in relation to the external world. Let us try to consider from this relativistic perspective the traditional oppositions, apparently impossible to resolve: truth and non-truth, appearance and reality, identity and difference, weak thought and strong thought, etc. Such dichotomies imply a “black and white” world, easier to grasp and express logically, but they do not account for the qualitative nature of phenomena – colours and shades. Traditional metaphysical thought simplifies the word in order to express its essence: from the complexity of natural phenomena, fixed realities emerge that cannot be reduced to any underlying system. “Nature” is the result of a conceptual creation, it is an idea that derives from an implicit frame of reference: our body. The bodily schema brings to light our first ecological coordinates.

From a certain point of view, there is an element of extraneousness from nature, since I am myself and my body, and not that other thing which is the external world; but we should not interpret this dichotomically. The appearance of something can be considered in terms of truth within a given perspective

frame of reference: perception.⁷ In the analysis of this topic we will consider those scholars that somehow appear “heretical” in respect to the Husserlian phenomenological tradition: Metzger and Koffka. The latter shows how things do not fill our spacio-temporal environment: there is something between things and beyond them.” In order to have a convenient term for this, we shall call it the framework, so that, disregarding the great variety of things, we can divide the behavioural environment into things and framework”.⁸ Koffka specifies both the sense of the notion of “frame of reference” within phenomenology of perception and the meaning of the relationship between subject, the thing and the external world.

To clarify the sense of the object and the external world within phenomenology of perception, we can take a further conceptual step, building on Metzger’s notion of “the encountered” : in this sense perception is unamendable, not susceptible to modifications that are dependent on voluntary and intentional subjective acts. In describing the characteristics of *the encountered*, in opposition to the merely *represented*,⁹ Metzger invites us to accept “immediate data” the way

⁷ In the following analysis I will resume and develop the notion of frame of reference as expressed in my book: Luca Taddio, *Fenomenologia eretica* (Mimesis, 2011).

⁸ See Kurt Koffka, *Principles of Gestalt Psychology*, (Routledge, 1935) p.72. See also: James J. Gibson, *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception* (Houghton Mifflin, 1979).

⁹ See Wolfgang Metzger, *Psychologie* (Steinkopff, 1941)

it is; in spite of its non-habitual, unattended, illogical or senseless appearance [...]” . It corresponds to what we have experience of: the external world, the objects that we touch, the beings that act in it, but also the events that take shape in front of us. This is the phenomenal world, namely, a complex reality the description of which cannot be entirely reduced to the physical level.

In the descriptive practice of phenomenology of perception, natural language appears suitable to grasp the sense of the phenomenal appearance of the world. Abstract and formal language distances us from the intuitive and sensible aspect of things, the sense and expressive richness of which are perhaps rendered in poetry and literary prose. Perception has a certain inherent *vagueness* that, compared to formal languages, natural language expresses with rigour and rationale, where expressions such as “few” and “many” , “light” and “dark” , “heavy” and “light” , “cold” and “warm” and so forth, possess a precise conformity to our way of practicing the world, of living and expressing it. Phenomenology, therefore, brings us constantly back to our *beginning*: it is capable of incessantly renewing the sense origin of the thing. Immediate experience is our first frame of reference: it guides us through the world and determines the sense of our actions. We think of this beginning as a relation to a given ecological system that determines a form of life. What should be clarified is not the evolutionary premise, but the notion of “immediate experience” as the basis of our being individuals,

relatively autonomous in respect to a system integrated in the surrounding environment.

Metzger further clarifies the phenomenological meaning of a frame of reference, when he asserts that: 1) “Every single object is found inside a determined relationship with a ‘frame of reference’, understood as the environment in which the object is and moves, and which determines its location, direction and measure” . The identification-localisation of each part and the measurement of the world are based on the stability of the perceptive frame of reference, not vice versa. This determines the meaning of the frames of reference. 2) We can conceive of a frame of reference as a determined structure, relatively stable and defined, and not as a sort of container that can be filled in different ways “In order to form frames of reference and their particular structure, the organism possesses specific conditions and limits that vary along with the sensory field and the type of content.”¹⁰

Therefore a frame of reference is not fixed *a priori*: order and stability are determined by the existing global conditions. Every relationship within the frame of reference conditions and structures it, but at the same time it becomes the condition for that possibility to occur. For example, every figure determines its background, but at the same time the background itself grants the condition of possibility for that figure to subsist: the background is not such without the figure. The figure determines its being a

¹⁰ Ibid, pp. 174-175.

shape in the relation between internal and external: it acts by its very nature like a reversible force-field. The meaning of *Gestalt* in this sense is intimately related to the notion of a frame of reference as its field of action. This force-field resembles the relationship among magnets and iron filing: a force acts upon it and an orderly and regular action field comes to be structured.

7.

Perception guides our behaviour in the surrounding environment. This – as I have said – represents our first frame of reference. Perception does not possess the rigour demanded by philosophical thought. Compared to commonsense, the degree of certainty aspired to by philosophical analysis is aimed at eliminating all doubts, with the objective of establishing incontrovertible knowledge, safe from scepticism. On what basis do we choose one parameter of certainty over another? We could answer through Wittgenstein that “The truth of certain empirical propositions belongs to our frame of reference”¹¹ The notion of frame of reference is fundamental not only from a linguistic point of view - in *Philosophical Investigations* Wittgenstein affirms that “The common behaviour of mankind is the system of reference by means of which

¹¹ Ludwig Wittgenstein, *On Certainty* (Blackwell, 1969) § 83

we interpret an unknown language.”¹² - but also from a perceptive point of view.

The incommensurability between language and world is more apparent than real, since every truth implies and presupposes a frame of reference. Here is a new assignment for philosophy: to show the implicit frame of reference in the sciences and in every theory of knowledge. The possibility of doubting the external world follows the same logic: it lies within two conflicting frames of reference (the logic one and the perceptive one). Wittgenstein’s idea is that the doubt lies only on that which is doubtless. Doubt can manifest itself only inside a language game, in a common and shared frame of reference. This thesis is not limited to asserting that our language’s coordinates, such as grammar, are anchored to a set of contingent propositions that we are not allowed to doubt; instead it implies that these propositions belong to a grammar of language, since they are the condition of its application to the world: “The truth of certain empirical propositions belongs to our frame of reference”¹³.

We should therefore recognise the logical (grammatical) function of propositions that describe our language as a shared image of the world, that is, the background on which truth and falsity are compared. “A doubt about existence only works in a language-game”; in order to doubt the existence of something “we still need an object that ex-

¹² Ludwig Wittgenstein, *Philosophische Untersuchungen* (Blackwell, 1953) § 206.

¹³ *Ibid.*, § 83.

ists".¹⁴ This means that "If you tried to doubt everything you would not get as far as doubting anything" and that "the game of doubting itself presupposes certainty".¹⁵ All of our speculations are oriented so as to keep some thoughts free from doubt: "the *questions* that we raise and our *doubts* depend on the fact that some propositions are exempt from doubt, are as it were like hinges on which those turn".¹⁶ But how does the trick work here? Once immediate experience determines our first spacial and temporal frame of reference and at the same time the semantic field of doubt, it also determines the degree of coherence of the false world. When we doubt we do not hold the same frame of reference.

In short: *logos* is functional to a frame of reference; the logical value of doubt conforms to the experience that presupposes it; *logos* does not grant knowledge *per se*; the phenomenological frame of reference determines the degree of reality and sense in the doubt.

Perception, which *per se* is not reducible to anything else, is a prime datum and constitutes an autonomous frame of reference. Our action in relation to the thing focuses our attention on its possible aspects and uses, but its appearance is also the prerequisite for its being an inter-subjectively shareable object. On this basis the others - who with us make use of the "public-ity" of the observed

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, § 24 e § 56. See also: Luigi Perissinotto, *Logica e immagine del mondo* (Guerini, 1991), 113.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, § 115.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, § 341. (emphasis added)

object - can request additional specifications in respect to that "healthy vagueness" that distinguishes our perceptive experience of the thing. This is how perception constitutes a shared frame of reference. The modes of appearing of phenomenal reality constitute our "faith" in the existence of an external world. What we share with the others is the appearance of the thing that allows us to pinpoint language to the world.

Let us consider our experience as such: by staying inside this frame of reference, we do not perceive any contraposition between the physical foundation and the appearance of observed thing. More so, we are inside a game of exclusion: we see aspects of the object, and the matter we touch is nothing but a sub-set of the larger one given to us by phenomena. Our experience is not presented abstractly in different degrees of complexity nor in layers, but it has *prospective* degrees

and layers of complexity: in order to see the materiality of a painting we need to stand a few centimetres away from the painting, and this is not the ideal distance for observation. There is a correct distance we need to respect in order to see it and appreciate it: neither too close nor too far away.

8.

Visual perception is by definition something which can be shown; it circumscribes the meaning of visual perception. If someone asserts to see something that he/she cannot point at, an anomaly is created that can be clarified

through linguistic interaction: through a complex back-and-forth between language and the world and between us and the others. To point the finger in a direction, according to the critics of ostension, is an inaccurate gesture since it does not indicate the designed object, but the series of phenomena that make it up. Hypothetically, the spectator could ask what we are pointing at: form, colour, dimensions? Nevertheless, this critique does not take in consideration the ecological frame of reference of the subject (rather than satisfying a gnoseologic need, pointing at something has practical purposes of communicative economy), nor the modes of appearance of the phenomenon: in direct observation “no object appears as a sum or cluster of properties: the object appears as a unity”.¹⁷

The theory of perception is tied to the topic of the body, as the body already is perception: we are our own body and it is not a thing for us, but that which the thing is given to. The body is not something internal or external, but it is the implicit frame of reference that defines in and out, right and left, high and low; from it, concepts acquire a sense for us. The body determines a frame of reference, ours, that intertwines with things and people that - like us - create actions, spaces and times around existence.¹⁸

In order to establish the truth of a description we must specify the frame of refer-

ence in which it is inscribed: if we speak of something as real, referring to what we experience directly, the description will be correct or incorrect depending on the adopted frame of reference. Such relativism is the very basis for every objectification of reality. If we confuse what we know about something with what appears directly, the description of the appearance of a thing in the external world will be invalidated by the stimulus error as described by Köhler.¹⁹ *The negation of a proposition within a larger or different frame of reference does not negate the truth of that proposition, since it remains true within its initial frame of reference.* The proposition should be judged within the same frame of reference, which should not be adopted uncritically, but should be specified and delimited.

A phenomenon which is experienced *iuxta propria principia* shows how, on this basis, the subjective and objective poles of the appearance of the thing are the result of the frame of reference implicit in the description of the problem, depending on the use we want to make of it.²⁰ The problem contributes to the determination of the right frame of reference: it is a function of the problem itself. Starting from the phenomenal structure of the thing the pole can be “subjective” or “objective” according to the assumed frame of reference: the definition of a polarity in absolute terms makes the other one

¹⁷ See Paolo Bozzi, *Scritti sul realismo*, in L. Taddio (ed.) (Mimesis, 2013), 80.

¹⁸ See Maurice Merleau-Ponty, *Phénoménologie de la perception* (Gallimard, 1945), 277.

¹⁹ See. Wolfgang Köhler, *Gestalt Psychology* (Liveright, 1929).

²⁰ Here a form of “neutral monism” is implicit, as it was already present in Mach and James.

aporetic. The sceptic doubt is no exception and is configured as creating absolutes out of a frame of reference; the hyperbolic doubt arises when two different frames of reference are conflicting, the transcendental experience of the evil daemon represents the metaphysics underlying immediate experience. The sense of the doubt can be re-established by coordinating correctly the logical and aesthetic orders in respect to the doubted thing.

In the IV book of *De rerum Natura* Lucretius describes a horse that stops in the middle of a river; the knight looks at the legs of the horse and, after a while, the water appears still while he feels as if himself and the horse were “running away”. This phenomenon takes the name of “illusion of movement”. Anybody riding the horse and looking at the water after a while would have the impression of being on a boat cutting through the water: the water becomes the frame of reference and you feel the movement. The same thing happens at the train station: when a train on another track is leaving, we have the impression of moving in the opposite direction. Lucretius, incidentally, reveals to be an extraordinary observer. It is true because it is there. This is the encountered and unamendable world, and it is true today as it was in the first century B.C.: today, just like then, we rediscover the same facts.

In antiquity the capacity to observe seems to have been intact, while our sad pragmatism today forces us to pay attention to certain aspects rather than others, to neglect the objects in their phenomenological fullness in

order to positively speculate on something useful to us, on which we can act in order to obtain certain goals. For this reason Merleau-Ponty thought that painters could teach philosophers: for the former, the centrality of *logos* gives way to the gaze and the silent observation of things. Through perception we give voice back to the expressive form of the world, which - through language - contemporaneously links conceptual and phenomenal frames of reference together. *Every proposition entails an implicit frame of reference which determines the series of one's own measures of judgement.* Should we retrieve our question on truth at this point? We could say that the task of a proposed new realism is also the task of a new phenomenology: to capture the frames of reference immanent in our form of life.